

The Effectiveness of Pastoral Visits: Case on Churches in Papua

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Abstract

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This paper reviews the effectiveness of pastoral visits during the COVID-19 pandemic. This study is interesting as viewed from the spiritual aspect; the author finds that the worship order in the Church has been changed in Covid-19 era. Elemental worship is abolished. Also, sunday school children should try to follow worship through online worship. In addition, several worship programs and other Church congregations cannot be carried out due to the spread of COVID-19. The governing body of the Jama'at also cannot visit the sick and the grieving. During the spread of COVID-19 the congregation needs ministry to support faith growth. Therefore, this study was conducted to find the effectiveness of pastoral visits. This study was conducted in Papuan church. On the other word, Churches in Papua are sampling of the study.

1. Introduction

Pastors have a duty to recognize the congregation's spiritual growth as church leaders. The realization of this requires strong connections, which may be established through making pastoral visits, and cannot be achieved just by focusing on sermons in worship. According to Clinebell (2006, p. 96), the pastoral visitation ministry can enhance the warmth of the pastor's ministry during church services. By paying attention and making visits, the pastor maintains and strengthens the mentoring connection. In an endeavor to defend and care for the church, pastoral visits become a driving factor for pastors in pastoral ministry (Riemer, 2005, p. 9). Particularly for rookie pastors in their area of ministry, visits are a great way for pastors to get to know the congregation. Through these visits, the pastor learns about the congregation's spiritual needs and expectations for church services, allowing him to establish objectives and plans that are appropriate for these requirements (Cowles, 1977, p. 13; Kosta & Djadi, 2011; Pranoto et al., 2018).

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Meanwhile, the visiting service is a recognized church practice that is crucial to building strong bonds with its congregations, according to Mimery (1996, p. 53). The two parties' interaction enables the pastor or church administration to understand the circumstances that his congregations are facing, enabling the church to effectively assist them. The pastoral ministry will be successful if the pastor is aware of and comprehends the needs of the congregation in order to develop pastoral ministries that are pertinent and suitable. Such offerings will boost congregational loyalty to the church and congregational pleasure with church services (Panjaitan & Siahaan, 2017).

The purpose of pastoral visits carried out by church pastors is to lead church members to perfection; Colossians 1:28 says: "He is the one we preach, when we teach everyone in all wisdom, to lead everyone to perfection in Christ. ." It should be remembered that in pastoral visits, several main principles are the responsibility of a pastor. They are conveying the Word of God to church members in need, praying, strengthening, and teaching them to become faithful to God and always put God first. Preaching and the intercession of a pastor is not enough to bring congregation members to spiritual growth, especially during this time of the spread of COVID-19.

Many concerns have arisen from the state of the spread of COVID-19. W. Stanley Heath says that Paul invites church to grow in faith to experience true peace. In growing faith, we will experience true peace. Because of the many activities carried out, pastoral visits are often carried out ineffectively, and the congregation's spiritual growth during the spread of COVID-19 is less visible to every individual in the congregation. Based on the consideration, this paper is presented.

2. Materials and Methods

Materials

Visiting is a form of Evangelization by Presencia.

Evangelical Church is a concrete action of the Church to declare and proclaim the good news of the coming of the Kingdom of God, both by Word and deed, to people worldwide. Jesus himself did the first preaching of the good news. He, who is God, has come and dwelt among men and preached every glad tidying of the kingdom of God to men. So this preaching is done by being present among humans. This term came to be known as presence for spiritual development.

The congregation's spiritual development is impacted by attending services. According to Nuh, Darmawan, and Sujoko's (2019) explanation, one pastoral service that promoted church development at GKII Tandang was visiting. The findings of Susanto's study (2016), further demonstrate that attendance at services contributes to a church's expansion. According to Panjaitan & Siahaan (2017, p. 10), many members who are often sluggish to attend church are revived to do so after receiving visits from the spiritual pastor.

Visiting is a service that God has assigned to the Church.

A visit is a human act to build and develop relationships between people. By looking at the positive things from visits, the church places visit into religious activities to maintain the continuity of church life by paying attention to the congregation's life and placing the congregation in the most important position in the life of the Church. According to Rostrina Pakpahan, visiting must be understood because a visit is a form of evangelization by the presence and a visit is a service assigned by God to the Church. We must do things that have to do with God's Word during the visit. It is stated that we

must do the things seen in the light of God's Word. It means that whatever is discussed in the visit, everything must occur in light of God's Word because we have a conversation before God.

On the other side, etymologically, pastoral comes from the word pastor (Latin), which means Shepherd (Celessi, 2012). It means that pastoral is an adjective, a "shepherd" trait. Then everything that becomes the work of a shepherd in serving the people becomes a pastoral scope. Everything related to the Pastor's duty to the people becomes the pastoral scope (preaching, catechesis, formation, visits, missions, etc.). The religious principles are forgiveness, acceptance, and atonement, not judgment, rejection, or exclusion.

It can be concluded that pastoral visits are essential as activities of pastors in serving the people to build and develop relationships between people. Pastoral visits are essential. Therefore, church leaders must be able to design an efficient and effective pastoral visit plan.

Research Method

This study uses a descriptive method with a quantitative approach. Descriptive research is research that tries to describe a symptom, event, and event that is happening at present, where the researcher tries to photograph the events and events that are the center of attention and then describe them as they are.

Meanwhile, what is meant by the quantitative approach is the approach used in research by measuring the indicators of the research variables so that an overview is obtained between these variables. The purpose of the quantitative approach is to measure the dimensions to be studied.

This quantitative descriptive research aims to make a systematic, factual, and accurate description, picture, or painting of the facts, characteristics, and relationships between the investigated phenomena. Next, it describes the independent variables and the dependent variable

The independent variable is measured based on the number of factors or parts that determine and influence some existing data or the emergence of other factors, which are called the dependent variable. In this study, the independent variables are the Effectiveness of Pastoral Visits with sub-variables as follows:

- a. Pray before and after
- b. Think of a general purpose for visiting
- c. Setting goals, number of visits
- d. Determine the time of visit every week
- e. Set specific goals
- f. Organize visits in order of priority
- g. Using a list system, archive

On the other hand, the dependent variable is based on a large number of various parts or factors that appear to be influenced or determined by the presence of independent variables in this study. The dependent variable is the Spiritual Growth of the Congregation During the COVID-19 Period with the following sub-variables:

- a. Spiritual Aspect in terms of intellectual, emotional, and spiritual
- b. Aspects of the family include intellectual, emotional, and spiritual
- c. Financial aspects in terms of intellectual, emotional, and spiritual
- d. Social aspects in terms of intellectual, emotional, and spiritual

Furthermore, in this study, the authors used quantitative analysis through observation, heritage studies, interviews, and questionnaires, then analyzed quantitatively in the study as follows.

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$$P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100\%$$

P = Percentage
F = Frequency
N = Total

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Bible Standards About Pastoral Visits

In Psalm 36:10, David explains that the source of a leader's strength comes from God Himself. Psalm 36:10 is written, "For in You is the fountain of life, in Your light you see the light." Psalm 139:9-12 is written, "If I fly on the wings of the dawn and make my dwelling at the end of the sea, there your hand will lead me also, and your right hand will hold me. If I say, let the darkness overtake me and the light around me be night, then the darkness will not darken to You, and the night will be as bright as day; Darkness is like the day." A spiritual leader does not depend on himself but on the light of God and the strength obtained from God. A leader can carry out his shepherding well over all the trials and darkness that befalls him, but God's light always provides a way out precisely in all of this. In preparing for the visit, God was the example and the light to his troubles.

The Bible says that human nature is like that of sheep. Sheep have a wandering nature without a specific purpose (Isa 53:6, Ezek 34:6, and Zechariah 10:2). That is why sheep need a shepherd. The Shepherd must direct the sheep to a specific destination. Thus, a leader must develop an effective pastoral visit plan to be able to support the spiritual growth of the congregation during the time of the spread of COVID-19.

In the words of Psalm 46, it is also written, "God is for us a place of refuge and strength, as a helper in distress is very evident. Therefore we are not afraid though the earth's changes, though the mountains shake in the sea. However, the waters are stormy and foamy, though the mountains are shaken by their tempest." We need guidance as humans who are full of limitations and realize that there is a greater power that governs everything. Shepherds and Servants of God who have been chosen and prepared by God have a massive role in carrying out services for God's work in this world, especially in supporting the congregation during the spread of COVID-19. One of the crucial tasks of the Church for Pastors and Servants of God is to carry out pastoral visiting services.

Next, in John 21, Jesus told Peter three times: Feed My sheep. About 30 years later, Peter asked the elders, Shepherd the flock of God that is with you (1 Pet 5:2). The shepherding principles of John 10 include the sheep knowing their Shepherd (v. 14); knowing His voice (v. 4); listening to His voice (vv.3,16,27), and following Him (vv.4,27) because the Shepherd knows his sheep (vv.3,14,27); lead them (vv.3,4), and was willing to lay down His life for them (vv. 11,15,17). To be a shepherd means to involve his personal life with the lives of his sheep. In other words, involve oneself with the life of the congregation. Ingolf (1988) explains that in the New Testament, the Greek Word *episkeptomai* is translated several times to visit or visit. In Matthew 25:36, 43, and James 1:27. The Word has the meaning:

- Checking to increase understanding and introduction
- Reviewing to help and serve
- Engage in relationships with others.

Jesus, in Revelation 3:20, says "Look. I stood at the door and knocked; if anyone heard My voice and opened the door, I would come into him and eat with him, and he with Me". Therefore, a pastor should visit his congregation frequently to get to know and serve one another.

Our ministry must follow the example of Jesus. Jesus ate with the crowd, both sinners and non-sinners (Mark 2:15); Jesus prepared Himself "according to the lesson" he was going to give His disciples (Mark 4:10). Jesus walked with His disciples (Mark 4:10). :35-41), Jesus' ongoing way of life, and Jesus was sensitive to needs (Mark 5:21-24). It is not the size of the group that determines whom Jesus serves, but the needs that must be met as well as possible.

The Shepherd must choose the best things to fill the time (Ephesians 5:16). A Shepherd must have a visit plan. Jesus himself had plans for a visit. In the Bible, in Mark 1:37, when they found Him, they said, "Everyone is looking for You." But Jesus answered. "Let us go elsewhere, to the nearby towns, so that I may preach there, for this I have come." Jesus had a clear plan for the visit and carried out His plan well. A shepherd must have an effective plan and execute his plan well.

3.2 Field observation

Researcher made observations of the Shepherd from June 14, 2022, to September 29, 2022. Below are the Researcher's Observations.

Table 1
Results of Observations of Pastors on Effective Pastoral Visits.

Pastoral Observation Chart of the Effectiveness of Pastoral Visits									
No	Date	June				July			
		16	20	25	29	3	9	11	17
1.	Praying before and after pastoral visits	No							
2.	Thinking of a general purpose for visiting	No							
3.	Setting goals for the number of visits	No							
4.	Determining the time of visit every week	No							
5.	Defining specific goals	No							
6.	Organizing visits in order	No							
7.	Using a list system and archive	No							

The author observes visits by the Shepherd from June 16, 2022, to July 17, 2022. The author bases his observations on Ingouf's theory of effective teacher teaching and James Sire's theory of the discussion of COVID-19 from the perspective of believers in God. On June 16, 2022, the author observed that the Pastor did not carry out pastoral visits until July 17, 2022. It was due to fear and a transition period of overall change from the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak that had spread to the Jayapura area. The decision from the Central Government through the Ministry of Health that we remain vigilant and maintain health protocols until there is a further decision for us to be free from the COVID-19 pandemic. It is why the Pastor and all workers in the Church have not taken steps to program an activity plan, but worship and elements every week are still held in the church building.

The author provides a questionnaire to the board regarding effective pastoral visits by the Pastor and a questionnaire to the congregation regarding the growth of the congregation's faith. The author

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took data from five GBGP Baitel Abepura Jayapura assemblies and twenty-two GBGP Baitel Abepura Jayapura congregations.

For the questionnaire, the author uses a Likert Scale. Morisson (2018) explains that the writer must formulate several questions about a particular topic, and the respondent is asked to choose whether he strongly agrees, hesitates, disagrees, or strongly disagrees.

3.3 Board Questionnaire for Effective Pastoral Visits

Like the data the author has provided previously, the author distributes a questionnaire to the assembly by giving twenty-one questions. Twenty-one questions the author raised from seven points in an effective pastoral visit, according to Ingouf (1988). Below is a table of the results of the author's questionnaire.

Praying before and after planning a pastoral visit

Table 2

Prayer Questionnaire Table Before and After Planning Pastoral Visits

No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1.	Pastor praying before and after planning pastoral visit		
	a. Very agreed		
	b. Agree	5	100%
	c. Doubt	0	0%
	d. Not agree	0	0%
	e. Very Disagree	0	0%
	Total	5	100%
No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
2	Pastor praying before and after carrying out pastoral visits		
	a. Very agreed	5	100%
	b. Agree	0	0%
	c. Doubt	0	0%
	d. Not agree	0	0%
	e. Very Disagree	0	0%
	Total	5	100%
No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)

3	Pastor praying for the congregation during pastoral visits		
	a. Very agreed	5	100%
	b. Agree	0	0%
	c. Doubt	0	0%
	d. Not agree	0	0%
	e. Very Disagree	0	0%
Total		5	100%

From the questionnaire data above, five respondents with a percentage of 100% answered very well, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered correctly, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered doubtful, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered inappropriately, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered very inappropriately. In pastors' statement about praying before and after carrying out pastoral visits, five respondents, with a percentage of 100%, answered very satisfactorily. Moreover, respondents with a percentage of 0% answered appropriate, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered doubtfully, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered not appropriate, respondents with a percentage of 0% answered doubtfully, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% the percentage of 0% answered very inappropriately.

On the question above, five respondents with a percentage of 100% answered very well, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered correctly, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered doubtfully, 0 respondents with a percentage answered not appropriate, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered very inappropriately.

Thinking of a general purpose for visiting

Table 3
Questionnaire Table Thinking General Purpose to Visit

No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1.	Pastors pay attention to the aspects of advice, guidance, rebuke, comfort and encouragement about life as the general object of pastoral visits.		
	a. Very agreed		
	b. Agree	5	100%
	c. Doubt	0	0%
	d. Not agree	0	0%
	e. Very Disagree	0	0%
Total		5	100%
No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)

2.	The pastor discussed COVID-19 and provided advice, guidance, comfort and invitation as an additional form of general purpose to support the growth of the congregation's faith during the COVID-19 period.		
	a. Very agreed	5	100%
	b. Agree	0	0%
	c. Doubt	0	0%
	d. Not agree	0	0%
	e. Very Disagree	0	0%
	Total	5	100%
No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
3.	The pastor conveys his general purpose when carrying out direct or indirect pastoral visits clearly		
	a. Very agreed		
	b. Agree		
	c. Doubt	5	100%
	d. Not agree	0	0%
	e. Very Disagree	0	0%
		0	0%
		0	0%
	Total	0	100%

Relating to paying attention to aspects of advice, guidance, reprimand, consolation, and encouragement about life as a general goal of pastoral visits, five respondents answered very satisfactorily, with a percentage of 100%. It means 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered correctly, 0 with a percentage of 0% answered doubtfully, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered not appropriate, and 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered very inappropriately.

In the Pastor's statement about praying before and after carrying out pastoral visits, five respondents with a percentage of 100% answered very well, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered yes, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered doubtful, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered not appropriate. 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered very inappropriately.

In the Pastor's statement, he discussed COVID-19. He provided advice, guidance, reprimand, comfort, and invitation as an additional general goal of supporting the congregation's spiritual growth during a pandemic. Five respondents with a percentage of 100% answered very well, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered appropriate, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered doubtfully, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered not appropriate, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered very inappropriately.

The Pastor's statement conveys the general purpose of direct or indirect pastoral visits. Five respondents with a percentage of 100% answered very well, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered accordingly, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered doubtful, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered inappropriately, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered very inappropriately.

Setting Goals Number of Visits

Table 4
Questionnaire Determines Goal Number of Visits

No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1.	Pastors carry out pastoral visits every two weeks throughout the congregation		
	a. Very agreed	3	57%
	b. Agree	2	43%
	c. Doubt	0	0%
	d. Not agree	0	0%
	e. Very Disagree	0	0%
	Total	5	100%
No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
2.	Pastors carry out 30 - 45 minute pastoral visits on one visit		
	a. Very agreed		
	b. Agree	5	100%
	c. Doubt	0	0%
	d. Not agree	0	0%
	e. Very Disagree	0	0%
	Total	5	100%
No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)

3.	Pastors carry out visits in the afternoon, but are flexible (adjusted to the congregation's daily activity schedule)		
	a. Very agreed	5	100%
	b. Agree	0	0%
	c. Doubt	0	0%
	d. Not agree	0	0%
	e. Very Disagree	0	0%
Total		5	100%

Next, about carrying out visits every two weeks to the entire congregation, five respondents answered very well, with a percentage of 100%. 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered appropriate, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered doubtfully, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered not appropriate, and 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered very inappropriately.

For pastoral visits for 30-45 minutes in one visit, five respondents (100%) answered very well, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered yes, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered doubtful, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered no appropriate, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered strongly disagree.

About carrying out visits in the afternoon and/or being flexible (adjusted to the daily church schedule activities), five respondents (with a percentage of 100%) answered correctly. 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered correctly, 0 with a percentage of 0% answered doubtfully, 0 with a percentage of 0% answered not appropriate, and 0 with a percentage of 0% answered very inappropriately.

Determining Visit Time Every Week

Table 5
Determining Visit Time Every Week

No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1.	Pastors make pastoral visits three days a week, namely Wednesday, Thursday, Friday		
	a. Very agreed	5	100%
	b. Agree	0	0%
	c. Doubt	0	0%
	d. Not agree	0	0%
	e. Very Disagree	0	0%
Total		5	100%
No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)

2.	Pastors carry out pastoral visits to seventeen families in one week a. Very agreed b. Agree c. Doubt d. Not agree e. Very Disagree	5 0 0 0 0	100% 0% 0% 0% 0%
	Total	5	100%
No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
3.	Pastor communicates pastoral visit times to the congregation a. Very agreed b. Agree c. Doubt d. Not agree e. Very Disagree	3 2 0 0 0	71% 29% 0% 0% 0%
	Total	5	100%

In the Pastor's statement that the Pastor carries out pastoral visits three days a week, namely Wednesday, Thursday, and Friday, the answer is as follows. Five respondents with a percentage of 0% answered very well, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered yes, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered doubtfully, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered yes, a percentage of 0% answered not appropriate, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered very inappropriately.

In Shepherd's statement carrying out visits to seventeen families in one week, the responses are as follows. Five respondents with a percentage of 100% answered very well, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered appropriate, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered doubtfully, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered not appropriate, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered very inappropriately.

About communicating the time of pastoral visit to the congregation, three respondents, with a percentage of 71%, answered very satisfactorily. Meanwhile, two respondents with a percentage of 29% answered appropriate, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered doubtfully, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered not appropriate, and 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered very inappropriately.

Setting Specific Goals

Table 6
Questionnaire Determines Specific Goals

No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
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1.	Pastors plan specific goals in pastoral visits according to the needs of the congregation a. Very agreed b. Agree c. Doubt d. Not agree e. Very Disagree	5 0 0 0 0	100% 0% 0% 0% 0%
	Total		
No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
2.	Pastors openly receive communication regarding the special needs of the congregation in pastoral visits a. Very agreed b. Agree c. Doubt d. Not agree e. Very Disagree	5 0 0 0 0	100% 0% 0% 0% 0%
	Total	5	100%
No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
3.	Pastors are open to the needs of the congregation who require the Pastor's physical presence or other methods needed for specific purposes in pastoral visits a. Very agreed b. Agree c. Doubt d. Not agree e. Very Disagree	5 0 0 0 0	100% 0% 0% 0% 0%
	Total	5	100%

Regarding planning a particular purpose in pastoral visits with the congregation's needs, the responses are as follows. Five respondents with a percentage of 100% answered very well, 0

respondents with a percentage of 0% answered according to one, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered doubtfully, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered not appropriate, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered very inappropriately.

Regarding communication regarding the congregation's needs in pastoral visits, five respondents, with a percentage of 100%, answered very satisfactorily. None of the respondents answered appropriate, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered doubtfully, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered not appropriate, and 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered very inappropriately.

Five respondents answered correctly about the needs of the congregation that require the presence of the Pastor or other methods needed for unique purposes in pastoral visits. They all agree that physical presence and other ministry methods should be conducted.

Arranging Visits in Order

Table 7
The Questionnaire Table Arranges Visits According to an Order

No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1.	Pastors prioritize pastoral visits to church members		
	a. Very agreed		
	b. Agree	5	100%
	c. Doubt	0	0%
	d. Not agree	0	0%
	e. Very Disagree	0	0%
	Total	5	100%

No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
2.	The pastor plans the order of pastoral visits based on the area where the congregation lives		
	a. Very agreed	5	100%
	b. Agree	0	0%
	c. Doubt	0	0%
	d. Not agree	0	0%
	e. Very Disagree	0	0%
	Total	5	100%
No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)

3.	The pastor plans the order of pastoral visits based on the free schedule, hours of work and the needs of the congregation		
	a. Very agreed	5	100%
	b. Agree	0	0%
	c. Doubt	0	0%
	d. Not agree	0	0%
	e. Very Disagree	0	0%
Total		5	100%

On prioritizing pastoral visits to church congregation members, five respondents, with a percentage of 100%, answered very satisfactorily. All of them agree that pastoral visits must be prioritized.

Next, all respondents answered very well about planning the order of pastoral visits based on the area where the congregation lives. It is the same as planning the order of pastoral visits based on an empty schedule, hours of work, and the congregation's needs; five respondents, with a percentage of 100%, answered very satisfactorily.

Using Register System and/ or Archive

Table 8
Questionnaire table using a list system, archives

No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1.	The pastor writes down the subject of prayer as one of the important points in the archive of pastoral visit activities		
	a. Very agreed	3	57%
	b. Agree	2	43%
	c. Doubt	0	0%
	d. Not agree	0	0%
	e. Very Disagree	0	0%
Total		5	100%
No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)

2.	The pastor has a register, an archive of pastoral visitation activities signed by the pastor		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Very agreed b. Agree c. Doubt d. Not agree e. Very Disagree 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3 2 0 0 0 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 71% 29% 0% 0% 0%
	Total	5	100%
No.	Statement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
3.	The pastor includes verses for strengthening the Word that are used in the archives of pastoral visits		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Very agreed b. Agree c. Doubt d. Not agree e. Very Disagree 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 0 0 0 0 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 100% 0% 0% 0% 0%
	Total	5	100%

About noting the subject of prayer as one of the critical points in the archive of pastoral visit activities, three respondents, with a percentage of 57%, answered very satisfactorily. Two respondents, a percentage of 43%, answered correctly, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered doubtfully, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered not appropriate, and 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered very inappropriately.

About having a list and the archive of pastoral visit activities signed by the Pastor, three respondents, with a percentage of 71%, answered very satisfactorily. Meanwhile, two respondents with a percentage of 29% answered correctly, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered doubtfully, 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered inappropriately, and 0 respondents with a percentage of 0% answered very inappropriately. Next, all correspondents agree that pastors have to have verses to strengthen the Word used in pastoral visit activities.

4. Conclusion

Based on the observation of the effectiveness of pastoral visits, it turns out that three of the seven steps outlined by Ingrouf have not been implemented effectively in pastoral visits. The three steps that have not been implemented effectively are setting a goal for the number of visits each week and using an archive list system.

Viewed on the results of the questionnaire - on the spiritual growth of the congregation in terms of family, financial, social, and spiritual aspects by understanding it in intellectual, emotional, and

spiritual terms in each aspect- shows that the spiritual growth of the congregation still needs to be improved in terms of financial and social aspects in terms of intellectuals and vibrant congregation.

Moreover, viewed from the family and spiritual aspects, the congregation can understand it. However, the strengthening for the growth of the congregation's faith given by the Shepherd has not been optimal in supporting the congregation's spiritual growth during the spread of Covid-19. It shows that the congregation's spiritual growth has not been maximized and needs to be improved by increasing the effectiveness of pastoral visits by the Pastor.

The effectiveness of pastoral visits by pastors can grow the congregation's spirituality by paying attention to the quality of these pastoral visits. The author has discussed that effective and efficient steps are needed to achieve the desired visit goals. These steps can be found in Ingouf's (1988) theory of effective pastoral visits by the Pastor, which is very useful in positively influencing the congregation, both in terms of understanding and spiritual growth. As stated by James Sire, we can see the congregation's spiritual growth from a good understanding of the four aspects of human life affected by the spread of Covid-19, namely family, financial, social, and spiritual aspects. The author also finds that the theory stated by Ingrouf is an example of an effective pastoral visit. It does not only focus on the initial planning of pastoral visits but also the aspects of life that need to be considered in designing the content of a pastoral visit from beginning to end.

Next, efforts to increase the effectiveness of pastoral visits by pastors on the growth of the congregation's faith during the spread of Covid-19 are to look back at the seven things stated by Ingouf (1988) regarding practical pastoral visitation steps. When the Pastor can find the steps that need to be improved from the seven steps mentioned by Ingouf (1988), it is hoped that the Pastor can increase his pastoral visits, mainly in carrying out the steps that have not been maximized before. Pastors can make efforts in Papua toward the congregation's spiritual growth to improve three of Ingrouf's seven steps regarding effective pastoral visits, which are less than optimal in their implementation.

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